

Implementation of Sentimental Analysis Voice Feedback in Home Stay Management system using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract— Nowadays, rather than just travelling, people like to seek out the tranquilly and vibe of their vacation destination. Travelers engage in activities that provide them the chance to interact with locals and gain an authentic understanding of their culture and way of life. Homestays are one such means to cater the needs of tourists in all-inclusive as feel of home. Also, this home stay makes a suitable option for a team like family, friends. The purpose of the study is to reviving seasons and periods which makes more effective in homestay's guests. The study is conducted in the Munnar district of Idukki, Kerala. The study also examines the link between visitors' pleasure and their socioeconomic status. The study's findings back up recommendations for homestay operators and government officials that would increase visitor satisfaction levels and provide more amenities to the industry's growth.

Keywords—NLP, flask, sentimental analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

A nice home stay is family-friendly and should be enjoyed with friends. As the number of tourists and travel lovers grows, they prefer to stay in good, well-maintained hotels all over the region. Customers find the amenities offered by the home stay to be quite impressive, and this can result in either a negative or favorable review depending on the amenities and the quality of the service. The positive feedback from the customers enhances the home stay business by spreading positive reviews to their friends and family. So that makes a good impression on the home stay and grows its reputation of the home stay. Negative feedback will impact just the opposite of positive feedback and it will ruin the organization's reputation, So the feedback provided by the customer is very much important to an analyzer home stay business, and also it will help to improve the service and guide the staff by the managers.

The advanced form of feedback analysis is sentimental analysis. The proposed system the sentimental analysis is implemented the feedback gathered from the customers is depicted using a chart in the proposed system. We employ Natural Language Processing (NLP) for sentiment analysis. NLP is the area of computer science, and more specifically, the area of artificial intelligence (AI), that deals with enabling computers to comprehend written and spoken language in a manner comparable to that of humans' artificial intelligence (AI), which deals with giving computers the ability to understand the text and spoken language in the same way that humans do.

A. Natural Language Processing Nature

From one language to another, automatic translation, document classification, indexing, and summarization. Recognize emotion and viewpoint in voice and text-based data.

B. Sentimental Analysis

Sentiment analysis is the process of identifying, extracting, quantifying, and studying emotional states and important information using natural language processing, text analysis, computational linguistics, and biometrics. systematically.

C. Voice Feedback

Voice Feedback is the process of audio extracting, quantifying, and play a voice notification review to the customer who make the review. Systematically.

II. SENTIMENTAL ANALYSIS – NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Sentiment analysis, as the name suggests, means identifying the perspective or emotion behind a situation. Basically, it means analyzing and finding the emotions and intentions behind text, speech, and means of communication. We humans communicate in a variety of languages, but each language is merely an intermediary or means through which we seek to express ourselves. And we are attached to everything we say. It can be positive, negative, or neutral.

Suppose you have a fast-food chain that sells a variety of foods such as burger, sandwiches, and kulfi. They created a website that sells groceries and customers will be able to order groceries from his website and even leave reviews such as B. Do you like or dislike food?

User Review 1: I love this cheese sandwich, it's so good.

User Review 2: This chicken burger tastes so bad.

User Review 3: I ordered this pizza today.

The first review is positive and the company is doing well.

The second review is negative and the company should look into the burger section.

The third can be considered a neutral statement because it does not indicate whether the customer is satisfied.

We may infer from the reviews above that, if the business wants to boost total sales, it needs to concentrate more on creating and marketing sandwiches and enhancing the quality of its burgers.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A natural language processing model for sentimental analysis and data visualisation is what the defined model aims to create. Positive and negative input should be able to be categorised by the model. A training dataset is used to train the algorithm or model, and consumer feedback is used to generate the test data. By exposing the model to more datasets during training, we can improve its accuracy. As a result, a model that may be applied to feedback analysis is produced.

The feedback provided by the customers remains anonymous. That is, it is not possible to identify who provided the feedback.

The steps required for the proposed model:

1. Data gathering
2. Pre-processing
3. Model Creation
4. Model Evaluation
5. Final output

Data gathering

Customers can enter their feedback after checking out the room and it will be stored in the database. This data is used for sentimental analysis with the help of natural language processing.

Pre-processing

This is how all machine learning approaches operate. Data reduction, transformation, and cleaning are all included. Making our model effective is the major goal of the approach. The data is analysed to accurately classify the data for us.

1. *Data Cleaning* – First step in the data process. Noisy data is removed in this process
2. *Stop words removal* – The unimportant data and the data which is repeating are also removed. That is no impact on the result after removing the stopwords
3. *Splitting of Data* – After cleaning the data the next step is data splitting into training and test data sets and test data sets the training data set is used to enhance the performance of the data
4. *Model Generating* –Generating the model using the training data sets and it is used for processing the data
5. *Model Analysis* –Analysing the performance of the generated model
6. *Final output* –Generating the final output using our developed system

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Import the necessary packages

```

from flask import Flask, request,
render template

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from vaderSentiment.vaderSentiment
import SentimentIntensityAnalyzer

import nltk

import re

from nltk. corpus import stopwords
    
```

2. Getting data from the user

User can enter their feedback through the user interface

3. Convert to lowercase

By changing all of the text or data to lowercase, conversion of the feedback eliminates any unhelpful portions or noise in it.

4. Remove stopwords

Additionally deleted are the irrelevant and redundant data. After the stopwords are eliminated, that has no effect on the outcome.

4. Final result

4. Data visualisation

Making judgments based on the data from the conclusion is simple thanks to the feedback's visualisation, which gives a clearer picture of the feedback that was given. It is the data's graphical representation. Charts or other visual measurements could be used.

V. CONCLUSION

This article outlines a process for analysing customer or visitor feedback after they have stayed at a homestay or used a service it offers. Natural language processing is used to perform sentimental analysis in the suggested model. Additionally, the system offers consumers who submit reviews of the service anonymity. Since the users' identities are concealed, they can give honest comments.

With a larger dataset, the system will be more accurate and more efficient. The data set can be expanded and used as a reference for future work.

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